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PHYSICAL THERAPY IN THE TREATMENT OF FACIAL NERVE NEUROPATHY

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ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to studying the effectiveness of physical therapy in the treatment of facial nerve neuropathy.

Keywords: facial nerve neuropathy, physical therapy, massage, ultrasound, electrical stimulation, facial muscle paralysis, quality of life, treatment.

Problem statement.

The facial nerve (Latin: nervus facialis) provides innervation to all the facial muscles, the stapedius muscle of the middle ear, most exocrine glands of the head (except for the parotid glands), including the tear glands, nasal and oral mucosa glands. This structure also functions as a taste receptor for the anterior two-thirds of the tongue and provides sensitivity to a small area of the ear [3]. Bell's palsy is the result of damage to the facial nerve, which can be caused by frequent exposure to cold, infections, intoxications, or trauma. This condition was first described in 1836 by Scottish physiologist Charles Bell, and it was named after him. Bell's palsy is accompanied by serious physical and psychological problems such as facial asymmetry, drooling, and other symptoms that can affect the patient's social activity [12]. Facial nerve neuritis is an inflammatory lesion of the nerve that innervates the facial muscles on one side of the face [4]. As a result, weakness develops in the muscles, leading to a decrease (paresis) or complete absence (paralysis) of facial movements and causing facial asymmetry.

Facial nerve neuritis is the most common among cranial nerve disorders in children [5], while in adults, it ranks second among cranial nerve disorders. The prevalence of this condition among children is explained by the anatomical features of the facial nerve [5]: 1) in children, the fallopian canal is not yet fully formed, so the facial nerve exits practically under the

skin from the temporal bone, increasing the risk of injury compared to adults; 2) the nipple-like projection of the temporal bone is also not fully formed in children, making this nerve less protected from injury.

Currently, viruses are believed to play an important role in the development of facial nerve neuritis. Studies in recent years have shown that patients with this disease have increased titers of antibodies to viruses such as herpes simplex, Epstein-Barr, influenza, and adenoviruses in their blood. Neuritis often occurs as a result of hypothermia [4]. For a long time, the pathogenesis of facial neuropathy was explained by various theories, including vascular, inflammatory, and others [6]. Nowadays, facial neuropathy is considered as one of the variants of a tunnel syndrome. Recent studies confirm the sequence of changes that occur with this disease, namely: "ischemia, edema, compression" or "primary ischemia, edema, compression, secondary ischemia". The development of inflammation and edema leads to compression and ischemia of the facial nerve. Prolonged and pronounced compression of the nerve can result in demyelination and secondary degeneration of nerve fibers [5; 4; 11].

Clinical manifestations of facial nerve neuropathy depend on the level of nerve damage. The main clinical symptom is paresis or paralysis of the facial muscles on the corresponding side of the face, leading to facial asymmetry. In addition, ophthalmological symptoms such as inability to close the eye due to paralysis of the

eye's circular muscle, tearing, and drooling due to paralysis of the mouth's circular muscle on the affected side may occur [5; 8].

Research by Ukrainian scientist O.V. Bismak suggests that facial nerve damage can lead to irreversible tissue processes in the nerve. This type of nerve damage usually cannot be restored, which can lead to trophic disturbances in facial muscles [3]. In 10-25% of cases, after treatment for facial nerve neuropathy, the function of facial muscles is not completely restored, and in 18% of cases, a cosmetic defect is observed. Post-neuritic contracture is formed in 16% to 32% of cases [1].

The question of the treatment and rehabilitation of patients with facial nerve palsy still does not have a definitive answer. Physical rehabilitation can play an important role in restoring facial nerve function after its damage.

Objective: To determine the effectiveness of comprehensive physical rehabilitation in the treatment of facial nerve palsy.

Method

This study was conducted at the Ternopil Municipal Hospital No.2. The study included 20 patients with facial nerve palsy, 12 (55%) males and 8 (45%) females. The age of the examined patients ranged from 49 to 63 years. All patients underwent a comprehensive examination, which included questioning and examination. The House-Brackmann scale [7; 9] was used to assess the severity of facial nerve damage. The medical facility followed the relevant regulatory documents in determining the diagnosis and treatment of patients.

Results and Discussion

The general condition of patients with facial nerve palsy who were examined was characterized by the following impairments: inability to fully close the eye on the affected side, weak facial muscle movements, unevenness of the face at rest, and absence of forehead movements. Upon admission to the hospital, all patients had a similar level of severity of facial nerve palsy, including severe dysfunction corresponding to 5 points on the House-Brackmann scale.

In addition to standard treatment for all patients with facial nerve palsy, physical rehabilitation measures were applied to restore normal tone of facial muscles, function of eyelids, and overall body tone. A physical rehabilitation program was developed, which included morning exercises, sound therapy, facial muscle exercises, therapeutic massage, self-massage, and physiotherapy measures.

The goal of physical therapy was to restore independent movements of the facial muscles and symmetry between the sides of the face in patients. To

achieve this goal, special exercises were used, starting with sound gymnastics and lip movements that are responsible for articulation, and then progressing to performing simple movements of facial muscles. Patients were recommended to practice sounds "b", "v", "p", "f", "z", which were combined with sounds "s" and "u" in front of a mirror. The criterion for successful treatment was the restoration of the ability of patients to whistle on exhaling and to purse their lips.

To restore independent movements of the facial muscles on the affected side and achieve maximum symmetry between the healthy and affected sides, patients performed special exercises for the facial muscles. These exercises included raising and lowering the eyebrow arch, inflating the cheek with pressure, closing and opening the eye, puckering the lips for whistling, protruding the tongue, baring the teeth, raising and furrowing the brow, as well as pulling the cheek with the mouth closed. Initially, these exercises were performed with the help of hands and then independently in front of a mirror up to 5 times a day. A physical therapist ensured the correct execution of the exercises to avoid the formation of pathological conditioned reflex connections. The pace of exercise was moderate. At the beginning of the course, 10-15 repetitions of each exercise were done, and then the number of repetitions increased by 3-5 every day until reaching 30-40 repetitions. The amount of hand assistance decreased gradually as the amplitude of independent movements and the strength of the paralyzed muscles' contraction increased to avoid fatigue in the affected muscles. Exercises for the facial muscles alternated with strengthening and respiratory exercises.

To maintain muscle tone on the affected side, therapeutic massage of the cervical-collar zone, face, and scalp was used. The massage began with therapeutic massage of the cervical-collar zone. Therapeutic massage of the chest-clavicular-nipple-shaped muscles included stroking, rubbing, and kneading.

To achieve an anti-inflammatory effect, improve blood and lymph circulation in the facial muscles, and improve the conductivity of the facial nerve, an ultra-high frequency (UHF) electric field was applied to the area of branching of the facial nerve. The UHF therapy was performed using the UHF-80-3 apparatus.

Table 1 contains a list of components of the physical rehabilitation program, the number of procedures, and their duration. The sequence of performing the procedures in the physical rehabilitation program corresponded to the order indicated in Table 1.

Table 1

medical rehabilitation services	The number of classes	The duration of the lesson	The total duration of the lesson	The room where the procedure takes place
Morning hygienic gymnastics	1	15-20 min.	20 min.	chamber
Audio gymnastics	1	5-10 min.	10 min.	physical therapy office
Gymnastics for facial muscles	1	15-20 min.	20 min.	physical therapy office
Therapeutic facial massage	1	15-20 min.	20 min.	massage room
Therapeutic scalp massage	1	15 min.	15 min.	massage room
UHF	1	10 min.	10 min.	office of physiotherapeutic procedures

After undergoing physical rehabilitation, certain changes were observed in the patients. According to the House-Brackmann scale, after 7 days of following the program, 4 (20%) patients did not show any noticeable improvement in their clinical condition. The severity of facial nerve impairment changed from 5 to 4 on the scale (indicating moderate dysfunction) in 12 (60%) patients, while in 4 (20%) patients, it changed from 5 to 3 (indicating mild dysfunction). After a 14-day course

of treatment and physical rehabilitation, significant improvements in health were observed in all patients. Following the physical rehabilitation program, 12 (60%) patients had moderate dysfunction of the facial nerve (rated 4 on the House-Brackmann scale), while 8 (40%) had mild dysfunction of the nerve (rated 3 on the House-Brackmann scale).

Table 2 contains the results of the impact of physical rehabilitation.

Table 2

Severity of urafacial nerve points	Volume of patients					
	Before rehabilitation		On the 7th day of rehabilitation		On the 14th day of rehabilitation	
	Abs.	%	Abs.	%	Abs.	%
5 (severe dysfunction)	20	100	4	20	0	0
4 (severe dysfunction)	0	0	12	60	20	60
3 (severe dysfunction)	0	0	4	20	8	40

The results of physical rehabilitation were analyzed separately by symptoms, and it was found that after 14 days of applying the physical rehabilitation program, all patients showed positive changes in individual indicators.

Conclusion

After using a complex of physical rehabilitation, which included morning hygiene exercises, sound gymnastics, facial muscle exercises, therapeutic massage of the neck-collar zone, facial massage, therapeutic massage of the hairy part of the head, electric field therapy for the branching area of the facial nerve, and self-massage of the face, restoration of moderate dysfunction of the facial nerve was achieved in 60% of cases and mild dysfunction in 40% of cases in all patients with severe nerve damage. In addition, all patients regained symmetry of the nasolabial folds and normal tear and salivary secretion. These results were achieved within 14 days of rehabilitation measures.

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